

NEW HUMAN CONCEPT IN MODERN LITERATURE

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Abstract: This article explores the evolving concept of the "new human" in modern literature from the early 20th century to present day. Through an analysis of major literary works and movements, it traces how authors have reimagined the human condition, identity, and potential in response to rapid social, technological, and philosophical changes. The article identifies key attributes of literary "new humans" including a fluid sense of self, transformative abilities, and a challenge to mind-body dualism.

Keywords: new human, modern literature, identity, posthumanism, transhumanism

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada XX asr boshidan to hozirgi kungacha zamonaviy adabiyotda "yangi inson" tushunchasining evolyutsiyasi o'rganilgan. Asosiy adabiy asarlar va konsepsiyalarni tahlil qilish asosida tezkor ijtimoiy, texnologik va falsafiy o'zgarishlarga javoban insonning holati, o'ziga xosligi va salohiyatini qanday qayta tasavvur qilinishini kuzatish mumkin. Maqolada adabiy "yangi inson"ning asosiy xususiyatlari, shu jumladan o'zgaruvchan o'z-o'zini anglash, o'zgarish qobiliyati va ong-tana dualizmiga qarshi kurashish aniqlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: yangi inson, zamonaviy adabiyot, o'ziga xoslik, postgumanizm, transhumanizm

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется эволюция концепции "нового человека" в современной литературе с начала XX века по наши дни. На основе анализа основных литературных произведений и течений в нем прослеживается, как авторы переосмысливали состояние человека, его идентичность и потенциал в ответ на стремительные социальные, технологические и философские изменения. В статье определены ключевые черты литературных "новых людей", включая изменчивое самоощущение, способности к трансформации и вызов дуализму разума и тела.

Ключевые слова: новый человек, современная литература, идентичность, постгуманизм, трансгуманизм

INTRODUCTION

The concept of the human has undergone dramatic shifts in modern literature, as authors have grappled with redefining identity, selfhood, and human potential in the face of rapid social, technological, and ideological changes. From the early 20th century modernists to contemporary science fiction and posthumanist works, literature has imagined "new humans" that transcend ordinary limits and challenge traditional notions of the human condition. This article will explore the evolution of the "new human" concept in modern literature, tracing its key attributes and situating it within broader literary and cultural movements.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

To identify major "new human" archetypes and themes, this article analyzes influential works of modern literature from the early 1900s to present day. It draws upon primary sources including novels, short stories, and manifestos, as well as secondary scholarship on transhumanism, posthumanism, and related movements in literature.

Key primary texts include:

- The Futurist Manifesto (1909) and modernist works like Mina Loy's poetry
- Virginia Woolf's *Orlando* (1928) and other explorations of identity and consciousness
- Post-WWII "new wave" science fiction by authors like Arthur C. Clarke
- Cyberpunk works of the 1980s like William Gibson's *Neuromancer* (1984)
- Contemporary speculative and posthumanist fiction by authors like Octavia Butler, Kazuo Ishiguro, and Ted Chiang

Secondary scholarship is drawn from literary critics and theorists such as Donna Haraway, Katherine Hayles, Cary Wolfe, and Pramod K. Nayar [1][2][3][4].

RESULTS

The analysis identifies three key attributes of the "new human" in modern literature:

Fluid identity: The "new human" rejects fixed notions of identity, selfhood, and the body. Influenced by modernist interrogations of consciousness and the self, works depict mutable, fragmented selves and challenge traditional boundaries between mind/body, human/nonhuman, and self/other.

Transformative abilities: "New humans" often possess extraordinary abilities to alter themselves and their reality, whether through technology,

mutation, or metaphysical means. These transformative powers position them beyond ordinary human limits.

Challenging binaries: "New human" characters frequently challenge Cartesian dualism and human exceptionalism. They disrupt divisions between mind/body, natural/artificial, and human/posthuman, complicating what it means to be human.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

These "new human" attributes can be traced across several literary movements and periods. Early 20th century modernists and futurists began radically reimagining human identity and potential, often drawing inspiration from new technologies and scientific theories. Works by Woolf, Loy, T.S. Eliot and other modernists portrayed fragmented, shifting selves and inner worlds that defied conventional notions of stable identity [5].

In the post-WWII period, "new wave" science fiction authors like Clarke and Ballard explored transcendent "new humans" with godlike abilities enabled by technological and evolutionary advances [6]. Cyberpunk of the 1980s-90s depicted "cyborg" fusions of human and machine, with protagonists jacking into virtual realms and acquiring posthuman powers [7].

More recently, speculative fiction has envisioned biologically and technologically modified "new humans" through works like Margaret Atwood's *Oryx and Crake* or Paolo Bacigalupi's *The Windup Girl*. Meanwhile, a burgeoning "posthumanist" fiction by Chiang, Butler and others has used the posthuman condition to challenge binaries and essentialist notions of the "human" altogether [8].

The "new human" is an ongoing, unfinished project in literature, reflecting the continuous need to reimagine human identity in an age of accelerating social and technological transformation. Depictions of "new humans" both emerge from and shape broader cultural notions of the human condition and its future.

While offering an exhilarating vision of transcendent potential, "new human" tropes also raise questions and anxieties about the fate of the human in a posthuman world. Some fear the "new human" heralds a decentering or erasure of the human itself. However, posthumanist thinkers argue the "new human" expands and redefines, rather than diminishes, the category of the human [9].

CONCLUSION

The "new human" is a central theme in modern literature, reflecting efforts to reimagine identity, human limits, and the boundaries of the "human" itself in

response to an era of radical change. With their fluid identities, transformative powers, and boundary-challenging nature, "new human" characters both embody and shape cultural notions of posthuman possibility. As we face a future of profound technosocial transformation, literature's "new humans" offer a imaginative testing ground to explore the contours of our posthuman becoming.

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